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OPEN EDUCATION ACROSS THE MEDITERRANEAN:

AN OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCE IN PRACTICE

Résumé. – Cet article présente et reflète l'expérience de la création du cours de renforcement des capacités « *Education ouverte: fondamentaux et approches* », produit dans le cadre du projet OpenMed avec le soutien du programme Erasmus + de l'Union européenne. Le cours vise à renforcer les capacités en Education ouverte et en ressources éducatives libres (REL) dans les universités de la région sud-méditerranéenne. Le cours engage 70 enseignants de quinze universités d'Egypte, de Jordanie, du Liban, du Maroc et de Palestine, et est mené par une approche d'apprentissage active, dans laquelle les activités d'apprentissage sont

complétées par des activités pratiques et un travail de projet final visant à démontrer comment les apprenants sont capables d'appliquer les connaissances acquises dans leurs activités d'enseignement quotidiennes. En outre, le cours est géré par des cercles locaux d'apprentissage, où des groupes d'enseignants interagissent avec des ressources et des activités en ligne et discutent de leurs échanges et de leurs idées, avec des facilitateurs appartenant à toutes les universités participantes et soutenus par les experts des thèmes des cours. Enfin, le cours est basé sur le modèle de Fink (2003), basé sur une taxonomie qui va au-delà de l'apprentissage par cœur ou de l'application directe des compétences pour développer des expériences d'apprentissage plus créatives, engageantes et réfléchies. Le cours, qui représente l'une des premières tentatives de formation de professeurs d'université et de doctorants dans le domaine de l'éducation ouverte dans la région méditerranéenne, a été conçu, développé et testé en collaboration entre les établissements d'enseignement supérieur d'Europe et de la Région sud- méditerranéenne, représentant une expérience authentique du développement de l'éducation ouverte multiculturelle, où les concepts, les approches et les méthodologies résultent des discussions et des négociations entre experts de différents contextes nationaux, linguistiques et culturels. Enfin, le cours fait l'objet de recherches pour saisir les expériences des participants tout au long de leur parcours d'apprentissage. Les perspectives des facilitateurs sont également recherchées, en tenant compte de la possibilité de mener une étude comparative des différents cercles d'apprentissage dans les régions.

Mots clés. – Education Ouverte, Ressources Éducatives libres, région sud-méditerranéenne, éducation supérieure, formation de professeurs

Summary. – This paper presents and reflects upon the experience of the creation of the capacity building course “Open Education: fundamentals and approaches”, produced within

the OpenMed project with the support of the Erasmus+ programme of the European Union. The course aims to build capacity in Open Education and Open Educational Resources (OER) among universities in the South-Mediterranean region. The course engages 70 university teachers from fifteen universities from Egypt, Jordan, Lebanon, Morocco and Palestine, and is run through an active learning approach, in which learning activities are complemented by hands-on activities and by the production of a final project work, aimed at demonstrating how learners are able to apply the acquired knowledge in their daily teaching activities. Further, the course is run through Local Learning Circles, wherein, groups of teachers engage with the online course materials and activities, and discuss their response and ideas or issues, with a facilitator, established in all the participating universities, supported by experts in the course themes. Finally, the course is grounded in Fink's model (2003), based on a taxonomy which goes beyond rote learning, or straightforward application of skills, towards the development of more creative, engaging and reflective learning experiences as both process and outcome. The course, which represents one of the first attempts to train university professors and PhD students in the field of open education in the Mediterranean region, has been designed, developed and tested in a fully collaborative way among higher education institutions from Europe and the South-Mediterranean region, representing a genuine experience of multicultural open education development, where concepts, approaches and methodologies have resulted from discussions and negotiations among experts with different national, linguistic and cultural backgrounds. Finally, the course is being researched to capture participants' experiences as they work through their learning journey. The facilitators' perspectives are also being sought, taking into account the opportunity to conduct comparative study of the different Learning Circles across regions.

Keywords. – Open Education, Open Educational Resources, South Mediterranean, Higher Education, teachers training

Introduction: the importance of Open Education for the Mediterranean region

Access to high quality education is key to the building of democracy, sustainable social and economic development, and intercultural dialogue within and beyond the South-Mediterranean region. Opening up education and sharing academic content will lead to a stronger integration of Higher Education systems, via the creation of relevant interrelated platforms of content, linking resources within or outside institutions. The use of ICT and Open Educational Resources (OER) has potential to guarantee a higher accessibility to education as well as diversifying the channels and means to learn and update the knowledge of learners. OER provide a strategic opportunity to improve the quality of education as well as facilitate policy dialogue, knowledge sharing and capacity building. The OpenMed project, an action supported by the Erasmus+ programme of the European Union, intends to contribute to facilitating access for everyone to teaching and learning contents produced by universities, thus overcoming the existing disparities in the South-Mediterranean region, with the purpose of supporting a more balanced and equitable socio-economic development.

Open Education represents freedom, transparency, equity and participation. The objectives within OpenMed, and of widening participation and build capacity in Open Education, are important to the national contexts of the Mediterranean countries. A baseline survey outlining the level of participation in Open Educational Practices (OEP) within the OpenMed partner institutions was performed at the inception phase of the project, to capture current practice at the time of completion (early 2016), and also to identify the future goals for the participating institutions. The results, included in a Compendium publication (Wimpenny et al. 2017), illustrate that the use of OER within the partner HEIs, is generally in line with current

practices more broadly, and thus has the potential to contribute to achieving future goals for extending OEP within the participating institutions.

In Egypt, each university has its own platform, and online programmes often emulate the more traditional Higher Education practices and pedagogies in that content is only available to enrolled students. National policies promote alternative approaches (i.e. more open access to e-learning and blended learning content) which can aim to make learning available without boundaries. The National Authority of Quality Assurance and Accreditation of Education is giving priority to the definition of a QA Mechanisms to ensure the quality of Open Education, and the Ministry of HE and the Supreme Council of Universities are playing an important role to enhance the adoption of open and distance education. In Morocco, there is already a significant critical mass of OE initiatives and the country could indeed play a leading role in the development of this field of practice in the South- Mediterranean and, more broadly, the Francophone African Higher Education system.

To face the massification of Higher Education and to encourage online production of quality learning, a national Moroccan platform called MUN (Moroccan University Numérique) is being created by the Ministry of Higher Education and the French Embassy in Morocco, with the support of FUN (France University Numérique) - a MOOC platform dedicated to Francophone universities. There are also several other projects in this field in Morocco, mainly aimed at facing the massification of education. However, better cohesion and coordination between universities is still needed in order to spread the principles of OE more widely and foster engagement with initiatives, as well as to prevent the duplication of efforts, e.g. when institutions are producing MOOCs. As a potential response to some of these issues, and as a spillover effect of OpenMed, the community of educators has developed a

declaration at a country level, the Declaration for Open Education in Morocco, which could help build a network of institutions and harness support from the government.

In Jordan, there is a clear intention of widening the spectrum of opportunities that can ensure that Open Education becomes a widely adopted in Higher Education, as they are already developing OER and Open courses especially in collaboration with EDRAAK, in particular to facilitate the design and uptake of OER and to provide disadvantaged groups and refugees with an open access to the educational system.

Open Education in Palestine is an important focus, yet challenges exist in relation to the lack of possibilities for the internationalisation of the Higher Education system, not least because living under occupation means restricted access for students from Gaza to attend West Bank Universities. Further, it is very difficult for international students and academics to attend both study or work in Palestine, which can impact scholarly exchange which also results in limited access to industry, to technological resources, and to natural resources. As the Palestinian economy is a captive one, there is thus a lack of resources for research and for teaching, and ‘Openness’ and Open Education is seen as essential to Palestine at both an educational and philosophical level.

Overall, the target of OpenMed, in line with the opening up of education and the sharing of academic content, is to develop a stronger integration of Higher Education systems across the Mediterranean region and beyond. In addition, the use of OER can guarantee a higher accessibility to education for people trying to access learning beyond the walls of the institution by diversifying the channels and means to learn.

The OpenMed course: approach and activities

The course *Open Education: fundamentals and approaches* aims to increase the capacity of universities from the South- Mediterranean, namely in Egypt, Jordan, Lebanon, Morocco and Palestine, to work with Open Educational Resources (OER) and Open Education approaches. The course is running its pilot phase from September 2017 to March 2018, involving 70 teachers from Higher Education Institutions in the South-Mediterranean. Following the pilot phase, the course will be improved, based on the feedback received by learners and facilitators. Further, the data gathered through the pilot, will be made openly available, both in the present structure (where universities have to *activate* the course by enrolling a number of professors) and in a self-learning mode, to allow independent learning by interested educators.

On successful completion of the course, learners will be able to:

- understand the potential advantages of adopting OER and open education approaches in different contexts,
- understand how content released under different kinds of open licenses can be reused, including how to apply open licenses to their own content, as well as search for, reuse and remix OER,
- understand what MOOCs are and how they can be produced,
- adapt OER and MOOCs to their specific context, and
- ways to incorporate open educational practices into their daily teaching.

The OpenMed course is taking a very practical and contextualised approach towards Open Education. In terms of applicability, the objective is that after having taken the course, learners shall be able to use OER and implement open teaching practices in their daily teaching work. In terms of contextualisation, the course starts from the perspective that

resources and courseware of good quality exist – mostly in English – that could be tailored and adapted to the needs of the learning communities of the Mediterranean region, increasing the effectiveness of content production through content contextualisation.

To make this possible, the course is adopting an active learning approach, composed of three phases. Phase one deals with an intense face-to-face element, bringing together the learners participating in the pilot phase of the course, with the aim of creating a learning community, including the introduction of the learning activities. During phase two, learners work through a number of online learning activities, during which they are expected to take the five course modules and complete the activities and assessment tasks proposed. This phase is run through Local Learning Circles (P2P University, 2015), meaning groups of learners who meet face to face to collaboratively run the online course and activities, that will be established in all the participating universities. Each Learning Circle is coordinated by a team of Local Facilitators, who are in charge of organising meetings, supporting learners, assessing activities, and reporting back to the community. In terms of content, the training programme covers the following themes: Introducing Openness in Education, Open Licensing and Copyright, Creating and reusing OER, Localising OER and MOOCs, and Open Educational Practices. In phase three, following the online learning experience, learners are expected to apply the skills they have acquired to develop a *final project work* aimed at opening up their teaching. The project work is fully integrated with the online phase and builds upon five steps that are taken at the end of each module: Step 1 is about making a pledge for opening up a course or their teaching, step 2 is about identifying open licenses to be applied to teaching/courses, step 3 deals with using OER in teaching, step 4 focuses on localising OER to a specific course/context, and step 5 is about developing an open teaching plan and sharing it with the community. Ideally, each project work should end up with the creation of some sort of OER, formally licensed and complemented by a tailored, open teaching strategy, that should

thereafter be used by the learners who produced them – as well as by other educators - within their teaching activities.

Reflections from the course stakeholders and analysis of learners' engagement in the course

Having already reached the end of the second phase of the course, some preliminary findings about the collaboration and learning dynamics have been realised, based on qualitative feedback - mainly provided by the Learning Circles facilitators, and on the analytics gathered from the course platform.

First, in general terms, learners have been actively participating in the pilot phase, not only by taking the online course and by working on their project work steps, but also by sharing their views and experiences through the course Forum. This is in line with the training needs identified at the outset of the course, and confirms that the active and collaborative approach taken by the course is fitting the learning style and preferences of the target participants.

Second, information sharing and collaborative learning is taking place, not only at the level of the Learning Circles within institutions – but also within the countries participating in the pilot, and also across countries, indicating that a community of practice approach has been initiated, based on the Peer2Peer University experience. This is a very encouraging finding that indicates the *collaboration readiness* of universities from the South-Mediterranean to engage in regional dialogues, learn from others' experiences and to discuss common challenges and innovative solutions.

Third, a good number of meaningful project works are being developed, both based on the work of individual learners and of small teams from the same Learning Circle. This is also encouraging and evidence contributing to the fact that the OpenMed course is not only

offering a meaningful learning experience to participants, but is also resulting in the creation of a set of artefacts (i.e. OER, new curriculums, new teaching strategies, etc.) that will represent an important *knowledge bank* for Open Education in the region.

Other feedback from the pilot course is also identifying how revisions and changes are required, in at least a couple of areas. First, the requested commitment is probably too high for busy professionals as university teachers, and this runs the risk of undermining the participation of some learners. Second, the facilitation role is also very time consuming, and requires a continuous commitment both during the two months of the online learning phase and during the subsequent project work phase.

Nonetheless, despite the aforementioned need to fine-tune a couple of things, the course approach, content and structure seem to work well, and in particular, are demonstrating institutional, inter-institutional and international collaboration around Open Education problems and solutions. This is an important achievement, if we consider that such a course is very new for the South-Mediterranean region, both in terms of content, approach and geographical coverage. Further, and going forward with the subsequent *open phase*, the aim is that the course should be a sustainable tool for *any* interested university and for individual learners, which will be a considerable achievement for the OpenMed project.

Discussion: the challenge of intercultural learning

The term *intercultural learning* can be understood at different levels. At a more literal level, intercultural learning refers to the individual process of acquiring knowledge, attitudes or behaviours, associated with interaction with different cultures. Very often, however, intercultural learning is understood in a broader context to refer to the way in which people

from different backgrounds are likely to live together peacefully, and to the process necessary to build such a society.

In this context, *learning* is therefore understood at a strictly individual level, but nevertheless emphasizes the unlimited nature of the process leading to an *intercultural* society. Educational systems, both formal and non-formal, use structured processes to facilitate learning. Learning experiences through training courses, seminars, group meetings, workshops, exchanges, etc. are examples of structured intercultural learning processes. If learning is viewed as a structured process, it seems logical to look at the methods involved. Researchers have repeatedly proven that individuals learn more from their own experiences - in situations involving knowledge, emotion and action. If we want to provide a learning space, it is important to propose methods that promote experience and reflection at all three levels.

The second term that appears in intercultural learning is that of *culture*. All theories of intercultural learning are based on the implicit or explicit idea of culture. All have in common the apprehension of culture as a human construct. Culture has been referred to as the *software* that individuals use on a daily basis; it is commonly described as the set of assumptions, values and basic norms that individuals possess. The concept of culture gives rise to a great deal of debate and controversy, both theoretical and practical. Very often, looking at culture requires looking at the interaction of cultures. Many authors have argued that if there is only one culture, we would not even think about culture. The apparent diversity of how people think, feel and act, makes us aware of culture. Therefore, we cannot think of culture simply as *culture*, but as *cultures*.

The OpenMed course in its general philosophy is a good example of intercultural learning. It has in fact created a learning community on Open Education and Open Educational

Resources. Many think that South-Mediterranean universities are Arab so there is no problem of interculturality since these countries share the same language, the same religion and the same culture. However, as pointed out, there is not one culture but several cultures. The Torino week, in which the pilot course was launched to a diverse group of more than 70 researchers, teachers and PhD students from Morocco, Egypt, Jordan, Palestine, Lebanon and Europe, was an opportunity to realise this state of affairs. Even the problem of terminology in Arabic arose between the Mashreq and the Maghreb - although it is the same written language. However, learning during this week, and especially during the online course that followed, showed that intercultural learning is possible, and that it can be enriched through the diversity of cultures.

The OpenMed course is an example of an intercultural learning experience in a number of ways. First, it is based on a pedagogical approach that privileges collaboration and reflection for individual learning, leaving space for collaborative learning and knowledge co-creation among learners from different cultural backgrounds. The course adopts Fink's integrated approach to course design, which is based on a taxonomy, which goes beyond rote learning, or straightforward application of skills, towards the development (Fink 2003) of more creative, engaging and reflective learning experiences as both process and outcome. In line with this, the aim for the OpenMed course is to create a significant learning experience for those involved, respecting and actually building upon the different cultural and contextual backgrounds of participants, enhancing social interactions with others (Fink 2003). Second, the course has been designed and produced in a fully collaborative fashion by a multi-national team composed of experts from the two shores of the Mediterranean, taking into account, as much as possible, the features and needs of the target population and the learning habits of each involved community. Third, the course contains a module on adaptation of OER and MOOCs to the specificities of the involved target communities. This module develops the

competences to adapt OER to the local contexts of the Middle East and the Maghreb, as well as to address an international audience. Both the contribution of intercultural communication skills and the management of multicultural groups are showcased. The module presents the concept of cultural distance (Berry 1997), the model of psychological acculturation (Hofstede 1980) and the theory of intergroup relations (Brewer 2000). Fourth, it is based on collaborative local Learning Circles, where learners have the possibility to customise and localise the course to their needs, encouraging the application of course content to real-life problems, having facilitators who care about the subject of open education and who desire to interact well with learners, and having good systems in place for feedback and assessment. Fifth, through the course discussion forum, the Learning Circles are encouraged to discuss about the themes of the course, through a concrete intercultural and peer to peer learning experience, allowing for exchange of views, practices, ideas among colleagues coming from different universities, countries and cultural settings.

Conclusions

Openness in Higher Education seems a common-sense approach for enabling equal and democratic access to knowledge, especially in countries such as the ones from the South-Mediterranean region where massification of Higher Education is an important trend. If universities really want to open up to larger students and researcher cohorts without dramatically increasing their cost for society, it is essential that the open sharing of resources is encouraged, that knowledge is shared and spread, and that teachers are stimulated to network and collaborate on course development.

The participation and interest being shown by the learners during the pilot phase of the OpenMed course and especially the regional collaboration dynamics that have emerged, represent an encouraging first step, since by using OERs teachers and students can collaborate on compiling course material and resources, opening up the classrooms to new forms of learning and increasing the potential for intercultural learning. But before this can be realised, we need – together with capacity building - a change in attitudes towards what we mean by teaching and learning at different levels. That is why the OpenMed course, which somehow can be described as the *capacity building backbone* of the OpenMed project, is being accompanied by other activities tackling both university leaders, who are developing institutional roadmaps for the adoption of Open Educational Practices, and the level of national and regional policy makers, who are being stimulated through discussions around a common Regional Roadmap for Open Education. The need to address these three levels: the teacher (micro), the institutional leaders (meso) and the policy makers (macro) is also emerging from the discussions that have been held during the online phase of the course as a concern of university educators. The challenge therefore, apart from improving the OpenMed course and making it a sustainable truly regional OER, is to combine all the bottom-up and top down actions initiated through the OpenMed project, to reach an actual systematic change in education practices in the Mediterranean region.

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